

Appendix A: Other clusters chemically compatible with ω Cen: [X/Fe] versus [Fe/H] planes

Figures A.1, A.2, A.3, and A.4, show the distributions in [X/Fe] versus [Fe/H] spaces for the other clusters that are chemically compatible with ω Cen together with NGC 6656 and NGC 6752 (see Figs. 2 and 3). These are respectively the metal-poor ones NGC 6809 and NGC 6273, and the metal-rich ones NGC 6205 and NGC 6254.

Fig. A.1: Chemical abundance relations for members of NGC 6809 (colour) and ω Cen (grey). The filled symbols show the reference sample of ω Cen (grey) and the stars of NGC 6809 (magenta) chemically compatible with it according to the GMM (see Sect. 4), while the empty ones (grey and orange colours) correspond to their outliers. The number of stars in each category is reported in parentheses.

Fig. A.2: Same as Fig. A.1 for NGC 6273.

Fig. A.3: Same as Fig. A.1 for NGC 6205.

Fig. A.4: Same as Fig. A.1 for NGC 6254.

Appendix B: Clusters chemically incompatible with ω Cen but with same metallicity: other examples

Figures B.1 and B.2 show the abundance ratios as a function of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, for the clusters Ter 9 and NGC 3201 that - together with NGC 5272 (see Fig. 6) - have a very low fraction of stars compatible with ω Cen, despite being in its metallicity range.

Fig. B.1: Chemical abundance relations for members of Ter 9 (colour) and ω Cen (grey). The filled symbols show the reference sample of ω Cen (grey) and the stars of Ter 9 (magenta) chemically compatible with it according to the GMM (see Sect. 4), while the empty ones (grey and orange colours) correspond to their outliers. The number of stars in each category is reported in parentheses. Ter 9 is an example of a globular cluster in the metallicity interval of ω Cen, which has a very low chemical compatibility with it.

Fig. B.2: Same as Fig. B.1, for NGC 3201.

Appendix C: Are the chemical abundances of a nuclear cluster representative of that of the host galaxy? The case of M 54 and the Sagittarius dwarf

Already in the introduction to this paper, we have evoked that - should a nuclear star cluster be representative, at least in part, of the chemical evolution of its host galaxy - the possibility opens up to use NSC to get a first description of the chemical characteristics of the galaxy to which the NSC belongs (or has belonged). In other words, if we can show that NSC and their host galaxies have similar chemical patterns, we can use the chemical properties of ω Cen to reconstruct at least part of the chemical patterns of its progenitor galaxy, *Nephele*, now completely dissolved among the Milky Way field stars.

In the case of the Milky Way, the comparison between the chemical abundances of the NSC and those of Galactic stellar populations is still ongoing, and is made difficult by the strong extinction present in the central regions of the Galaxy. Fortu-

nately, the APOGEE DR17 data offer us the opportunity to study another NSC-galaxy host system, the one consisting of the Sagittarius dwarf galaxy and NGC 6715 (M 54), its nuclear star cluster (see also Bellazzini et al. 2003, 2008; Alfaro-Cuello et al. 2019, 2020; Bellazzini et al. 2020; Kacharov et al. 2022). In this section, we present the results of this comparison.

For the Sagittarius galaxy, we used the APOGEE data presented in Hasselquist et al. (2021). In particular, their Table 2 provides the identifiers of stars belonging to the Sagittarius dwarf and its streams - according to their selection - which we cross-identified with the APOGEE DR17 catalogue to obtain their chemical abundances. From the retrieved sample, we then selected only stars with:

1. a signal-to-noise ratio $\text{SNREV} > 70$;
2. temperatures in the range $3500 \text{ K} < T_{\text{eff}} < 5500 \text{ K}$ and surface gravities $\log g < 3.6$;
3. APOGEE STARFLAG and APOGEE STARBAD = 0

Fig. C.1: $[X/Fe]$ versus $[Fe/H]$ planes for NGC 6715 (coloured stars), the nuclear star cluster of the Sagittarius dwarf galaxy. For comparison, the distribution of stars belonging to the Sagittarius dwarf is also shown as grey points. In each panel, the number of stars used to make the corresponding plot is given, both for NGC 6715 and for Sagittarius. Note that these numbers can vary from a panel to another, because the APOGEE quality flags on the corresponding abundances may lead to different selections. For each panel, individual error bars on $[Fe/H]$ and $[X/Fe]$ abundances, for NGC 6715, are also reported.

As for NGC 6715, we used the Schiavon et al. (2024) catalogue already used for all other Galactic globular clusters¹⁵, applying the same selections discussed in Sect 2. Fig. C.1 shows the result of this comparison. We can see from this figure that in all abundance planes the NGC 6715 chemical patterns as a function of $[Fe/H]$ follow very closely those of the Sagittarius galaxy. In particular:

- in the Sagittarius dwarf, α -elements as $[Ca/Fe]$, $[Mg/Fe]$, $[O/Fe]$ and $[Si/Fe]$ show a declining trend as a function of $[Fe/H]$, until $[Fe/H] \sim -0.9$ dex; for $[Fe/H]$ values above this limit, these patterns become flatter or with a “hook”-like shape. As explained by Hasselquist et al. (2021), these trends as a function of $[Fe/H]$ can be explained if the Sagittarius dwarf, after an initial burst of star formation occurred early on during its evolution, experienced a second, weaker burst about 10 Gyr after (see Figs. 9, 10 and 11 in their paper). This

point is in agreement with what has been found for the age and metallicity of the stellar populations of M 54 by Alfaro-Cuello et al. (2019): the metal-rich (young) component of the cluster is compatible with the second starburst of Sagittarius (which likely happened ~ 3 Gyr ago). Strikingly, our Fig. C.1 shows that the same trends for α -elements as a function of $[Fe/H]$ are present also in NGC 6715, with declining $[\alpha/Fe]$ ratios as a function of $[Fe/H]$ up to $[Fe/H] \sim -0.9$ dex, where the “hooked” profile appears. This indicates that – whatever the process of formation of NGC 6715 has been – this cluster has experienced the same star formation evolution, at similar efficiency, as that experienced by its parent galaxy. In particular, at late times, the ISM from which stars of NGC 6715 formed must have been polluted by SNeII, similarly to what happened in the ISM of Sagittarius, that is: the same kind of polluters (SNeII) must have contributed at the same time to enrich the gas reservoir of both systems, in order to produce in both of them the “hooked” pattern observed in the same metallicity range.

¹⁵ Note that Sagittarius has a few other suspected associated clusters such as Ter 8, Arp 2, NGC 5634, and Ter 7 whose data, however, are not available in the Schiavon et al. (2024) catalogue.

Fig. C.2: [Fe/H] distributions of the analysed APOGEE stars in NGC 6715 (colored histogram) and in the Sagittarius dwarf (grey histogram). Both histograms are normalised so that the integral of the density over the range is equal to one. The number of stars used to trace the two histograms is reported in parenthesis.

- More generally, the trends of [X/Fe] versus [Fe/H] observed in the Sagittarius dwarf, compared to those of the Milky Way, have led to suggest that the chemical enrichment in this galaxy may have been affected by higher Type Ia/Type II SNe ratio than in the MW, or by a top-light IMF (see, for example McWilliam et al. 2013; Hasselquist et al. 2021). Whatever the sources, or the combination of sources, responsible for the chemical enrichment of this galaxy, the same mechanisms must have been at work in NGC 6715 in order to produce the same trends for all the chemical elements shown in Fig. C.1.

From Fig. C.1, a few apparent differences are worth being discussed:

- the presence of a small percentage ($\sim 5\%$) of C-rich ($[C/Fe] \geq -0.2$) stars among the metal-rich ($[Fe/H] \geq -0.75$) population of Sagittarius. No C-rich counterpart is observed at similar metallicities in NGC 6715, but given the low number of stars with $[Fe/H] \geq -0.75$ in this cluster (11 in total), the absence of C-rich stars in this cluster is still statistically compatible with the 5% fraction observed in Sagittarius.
- the presence of a few Al-enhanced ($[Al/Fe] \geq 0.25$) stars in NGC 6715 (at $[Fe/H] \leq -1$, which are not present among the field (i.e. Sagittarius) population. Al-enhanced stars are commonly present in globular clusters. It is possible that a few of these stars may be present also in the Sagittarius galaxy (as the result of the mass loss experienced by some of its globular clusters) but given the overall limited number of Sag stars at $[Fe/H] \leq -1$ it is difficult to derive any robust conclusion.

Finally, we would like to draw the reader attention to the fact that, while in all [X/Fe]-[Fe/H] planes reported in Fig. C.1 the overlap between the chemical patterns of NGC 6715 and those of its host galaxy is impressive, if the comparison is made only on their MDFs, no similarities between the two are found (see Fig. C.2). This should discourage from comparing stellar populations based merely on a comparison of MDFs. Different stellar systems may be affected by different observational biases (which would then lead to changes of the intrinsic MDF

of these systems), or different dynamical evolutions may modify the MDFs of the systems over time, modulating them differently. In any case, the comparison between NGC 6715 and Sagittarius offers another example¹⁶ of the limited discriminatory power of MDFs to establish similarities or differences between stellar populations. Populations with the same chemical evolution can have different MDFs (i.e. different fractions of stars in a similar metallicity range) but this is not sufficient to exclude that they had similar chemical evolutions, as evidenced by the NGC 6715-Sagittarius comparison (Fig. C.1).

Appendix D: GCs chemically compatible with ω Cen: other elements

Figures D.1, D.2, D.3, D.4, D.5, and D.6 show for each GC chemically compatible with ω Cen, the distribution in [X/Fe] versus [Fe/H] planes where the different X elements are the others provided by APOGEE DR17 but not used in the GMM, namely: N, O, Na, S, Ti, V, Cr, Ni, and Ce. Although these abundances have been excluded for the reasons given in Sec 3, it is nevertheless interesting to see at least qualitatively how they compare with ω Cen (also shown). In general, for all the GCs, despite the larger uncertainties, the overlap with ω Cen also clearly occurs in these other chemical spaces.

The most striking case is that of NGC 6656 since, in addition to the fact that its superposition takes place in regions where ω Cen has its density peak, it also shows similar features even apart from the bulk of its stars. For instance:

- in both [N/Fe] and [S/Fe], two stars are detached from the others by being under-abundant (~ -0.5), thus populating the same region where we find a small group of ω Cen stars, also detached from the majority of the population;
- for [Na/Fe] and [V/Fe] values lower than -0.5 both ω Cen and NGC 6656 seem to trace a kind of demarcation line that decreases as [Fe/H] increases, below which we find no stars (see also NGC 6273);
- for $[Ti/Fe] \lesssim -0.5$, we can see a sort of bifurcation into two decreasing patterns (each consisting of two stars) similar to those of ω Cen but also a star with a Ti-excess comparable with the one observed in two ω Cen stars;
- a similar but perhaps more outstanding behaviour is what we observe for $[Ce/Fe] \lesssim -0.7$, where both NGC 6656 and ω Cen stars shape the same small declining tail towards higher [Fe/H] (also seen in NGC 6205 and NGC 6254).

Analogous peculiarities are also found in the other clusters chemically compatible with ω Cen. For instance, by looking at the metal-poor GCs defined in Sect. 4, we can see that NGC 6656 and NGC 6273 span the exact same range of [Cr/Fe] and [V/Fe] as ω Cen at equal [Fe/H], and even NGC 6809, despite its lower statistic compared to the other two, presents V-depleted and Cr-depleted stars like ω Cen. Regarding the metal-rich GCs, each has two Ni-poor stars at $[Fe/H] \sim -1.5$ and $[N/Fe] \sim -0.2$ that overlap with the similar Ni-deficient sequence in ω Cen; NGC 6205 even seems to follow this sequence with 2 stars with $[Ni/Fe] < -0.3$. Both NGC 6752 and NGC 6254 own a group of stars with [Na/Fe] and [V/Fe] values that fall in correspondence with the lowest boundary sequence drawn

¹⁶ To cite another example of this kind, we recall the reader that the MW bulge and thin+thick disc MDFs are different, while their patterns in [X/Fe] versus [Fe/H] planes, for a number of different chemical elements, show a remarkable agreement (see, for example, Bensby et al. 2010; Haywood et al. 2018; Bensby et al. 2021)

by ω Cen's stars. NGC 6205, on the other hand, features four V-enhanced stars spanning the exact same values as the V-rich stars of ω Cen in the corresponding $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ range ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.5$). In contrast, a clear under-abundance seen in this GC compatible with that observed in ω Cen is represented by three stars at $[\text{Cr}/\text{Fe}] < -0.5$. Finally, both NGC 6205 and NGC 6254 show a decreasing trend of $[\text{O}/\text{Fe}]$ with increasing $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ that resembles that observed for the more metal-poor stars in ω Cen.

Fig. D.1: $[\text{X}/\text{Fe}]$ versus $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ planes for NGC 6656 (black symbols), one of the GCs chemically compatible with ω Cen. Here, the different X elements are the others provided by APOGEE DR17 but NOT used in the GMM, namely: N, O, Na, S, Ti, V, Cr, Ni, and Ce. For comparison, the distribution of stars belonging to ω Cen is also shown as grey circles.

Fig. D.2: Same as Fig. D.1 for NGC 6809

Fig. D.3: Same as Fig. D.1 for NGC 6273.

Fig. D.4: Same as Fig. D.1 for NGC 6752.

Fig. D.5: Same as Fig. D.1 for NGC 6205.

Fig. D.6: Same as Fig. D.1 for NGC 6254.

Appendix F: On the chemical compatibility of ω Cen with the most massive satellites of the Milky Way

In Figs. F.1, F.2, F.3 and F.4, we show the comparison of the chemical patterns of ω Cen with those of the Large and Small Magellanic Clouds, Sagittarius and Fornax. In all plots, magenta symbols indicate stars of the aforementioned dwarfs which are chemically compatible with ω Centauri, while orange symbols indicate stars which are outliers of the ω Cen chemical domain, according to the GMM model.

Fig. F.1: Chemical abundance relations for members of LMC (colour) and ω Cen (grey). The filled symbols show the reference sample of ω Cen (grey) and the stars of LMC (magenta) chemically compatible with it according to the GMM (see Sect. 4), while the empty ones (grey and orange colours) correspond to their outliers. The number of stars in each category is reported in parentheses. For clarity, only stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1$ are shown.

Fig. F.2: Same as Fig. F.1, but for the SMC.

Fig. F.3: Same as Fig. F.1 and F.2 but for Sagittarius.

Fig. F.4: Same as Figs. F.1, F.2 and F.3 but Fornax.

Appendix G: Median abundances of GCs chemically compatible with ω Cen

Regarding GCs chemically compatible - with at least 60% of their stars - with ω Cen, Figures G.1 and G.2 show respectively their median and mode values of $[X/Fe]$ versus $[Fe/H]$ for the elements used in the GMM. For comparison, other GCs in our sample and all APOGEE stars are also shown. We show these quantities to stress the need to consider for each GC the complete distribution of stars in these chemical spaces when the aim is to find similarities between clusters linked to a common origin. In fact, as we can see considering medians or modes, even though ω Cen and clusters compatible with it share the same range of $[Fe/H]$ ($-2 < [Fe/H] \lesssim -1.5$), they do not show any distinct patterns from the rest of the GCs in the other elements. Furthermore, for some elements for which the spread is larger and the distribution of individual stars is more complex, for instance, Al, C, and K, depending on whether one considers means, medians, or modes, substantially different results are obtained. Thus, in addition to the overlap between ω Cen-compatible and non- ω Cen-compatible clusters, the choice of whether to use the median or the mode also impacts the results: if the distribution in a certain element has a density peak, the mode may be more indicative, but if the distribution is continuous or multimodal, the median should be preferred. Therefore, to obtain more robust results and to capture all the different peculiarities in the chemical evolution of a globular cluster, we believe that the most robust approach is to analyse star individual abundances.

Fig. G.1: Median $[X/Fe]$ versus $[Fe/H]$ for GCs chemically compatible - with at least 60% of their stars - with ω Cen; the different X elements are the ones used in the GMM, namely: Mg, Si, Ca, C, Al, K, and Mn. For comparison, other GCs in our sample (blue points) and all APOGEE stars (GCs' stars included, grey points) are also shown.

Fig. G.2: Mode $[X/Fe]$ versus $[Fe/H]$ for GCs chemically compatible - with at least 60% of their stars - with ω Cen; the different X elements are the ones used in the GMM, namely: Mg, Si, Ca, C, Al, K, and Mn. For comparison, other GCs in our sample (blue points) and all APOGEE stars (GCs' stars included, grey points) are also shown.